

THE IMPORTANCE OF MORALS AND ETHICS IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18642114>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th February 2026

Accepted: 12th February 2026

Online: 13th February 2026

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

No person lives outside of society, alone. He grows up, matures, lives among people, and throughout his life and work communicates with many people of various categories, with large and small labor communities. This arises from the need for a person to satisfy his daily life needs. Living in a community requires adherence to customs, traditions, and laws and regulations accepted in society. In this process, the objective relationship that arises between a person and society, that is, the complex of social relations - principles and norms of behavior, etiquette, and behavior, constitutes the essence of morality.

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Morality is a set of certain behaviors, etiquette, behavior, principles and norms that arise due to the objective relationship between a person and society, and that govern and regulate the life and work of each person on the basis of coordinating personal and common interests.

Morality is a social phenomenon that arose simultaneously with the emergence of human society as a social relationship serving the needs and interests of communities and individuals. In its historical development, it has performed the following tasks:

- a component of universal human culture in the form of activity that changes the natural qualities of a person;
- one of the foundations of the spiritual and social factor that comprehensively develops each person living in society;
- the best way to develop people's inner feelings and emotions, to understand universal human material and spiritual values, to preserve them and pass them on to future generations;
- a means of continuing traditions such as family duty, mutual respect, loyalty, honor, etc., existing in the family and everyday life, from generation to generation, etc.

The science of ethics is directly involved in the study of the above-mentioned issues, namely, morality and its role in the life of society. The science of ethics is a science that studies the origin, essence, characteristics, role in the development of society, and the laws of development, and consists of a set of knowledge that has been proven to be true in practice. Like other social sciences, it has its own laws and categories, through which it expresses its conclusions. The science of ethics consists of such components as the general theory of ethics, historical ethics, normative-value ethics, professional ethics, and the theory of moral education. The general theory of ethics studies the nature, essence, characteristics, components of morality, and its role in the development of society.

The role of morality in the life of society is determined by the following functions it performs: The regulatory function is the main function of morality. The regulatory function means guiding the activities of an individual, a service team, state and public institutions on the basis of moral norms existing in society. For this purpose, it relies on a number of tools: moral principles, public opinion, moral authority, traditions, customs, etc. Morality governs the behavior of not only an individual, but also the entire society.

Axiological function (evaluation) - as we noted above, any moral behavior is evaluated through a particular system of values. Based on the "moral-immoral", "good" point of view, actions, relationships, motives, views, personal qualities are evaluated. Morality also controls the assimilation of values by a person and their development.

The informational (cognitive) function is aimed at creating moral knowledge, and moral principles, norms, codes are a source of information about socio-moral values. At the same time, attention is paid to the issue of moral choice in ordinary and extreme situations, in conflict and crisis situations. Thus, morality helps to understand the world, man, his essence, the meaning of his life.

The educational function is that any educational system is, first of all, a system of moral education. Moral education brings moral norms, customs, traditions, and general patterns of behavior into a clear organizational system, transforms moral knowledge into moral beliefs, and teaches a creative approach to the application of moral knowledge and beliefs in specific situations. Thus, morality teaches not only to comply with norms and rules, but also to self-control. Here it should be noted that the separation of separate functions of morality is of a conditional nature. Because in real life they are manifested in harmony with each other. Morality simultaneously governs, educates, directs, etc. Moral knowledge is formed on the basis of an assessment of human relations and phenomena of social reality. The main criteria for this assessment are people's ideas about "what is good and what is bad." Such an assessment is characteristic of both society and an individual. Thus, social and individual systems arise from moral values. These systems are inextricably linked and manifest themselves differently in each person.

If a person's social value system prevails in his activities, he actively participates in social life, the principle of community prevails in his worldview. On the contrary, a person prioritizes his personal interests, the principle of individualism prevails in his worldview. Professional ethics is the study and application of moral norms, principles and qualities inherent in each profession. The theory of moral education studies the means and methods of implementing morality in life, based on the demands, needs, and interests of society..

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